

SECURITY SECTOR REFORM IN ETHIOPIA: A STUDY ON AMHARA NATIONAL REGIONAL STATE POLICE FORCE

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this study is to assess security sector reform in Ethiopia with a particular reference to the Amhara Regional Police Force. The central objective of this study was to explore the implementations, challenges and limitations of SSR in the Amhara Regional State Police Commission. The researcher employed qualitative research method with case study research design. The data was collected from primary and secondary sources. The participants of this study were selected via purposive sampling. The findings of the study show that SSR is currently implemented in the Amhara Regional State Police Commission having different forms. But, it is not in a position to improve the performance and service delivery of police force. The finding of the study also shows that the measures taken by the Commission and stakeholders to improve the reform program and service delivery of police are inadequate. The study also identified the major challenges of reform program and these are political interference, lack of competent leadership and lack of human and material resource. Lastly, the study suggested recommendations to the ANRS Police Commission, Stakeholders, and to the ANRS Council.

KEYWORDS

Security, SSR, Police, Police Commission, Amhara, Ethiopia

1. INTRODUCTION

Security sector reform as a concept was introduced after the 1990s by security experts and politicians in the world. It is originated from two spectrums. The first one is from the development community who were the advocators on the importance of security sector for economic development and democratization and the second one is from the field of civil-military relations who promote the holistic approach of security in Central and East Europe [13]. But, it was after the speech by Clare Short, the then UK's Secretary of State for the International Development in 1998 that security sector reform became a burning discourse among scholars, government officials, and institutions at all levels of the international community [6]. Security sector reform is a broader concept which encompasses institutions like the military, paramilitary, police, intelligence services, border guards, the judiciary and other governmental entities which are mandated to supervise these institutions [7].

The end of cold war had changed the types of conflict and security threats among the World community in general and developing nations in particular. Therefore, in order to manage such threats at all levels of the community, the concept of security sector reform was developed [24].

To this effect, the UN under the department of Security Council gives a due emphasis for security sector reform and assisted member states to adopt it in line with their national and regional context. Accordingly, the Security Council indicated that SSR is vital for states to consolidate their peace and stability, ensure rule of law and good governance as well as prevent countries from relapsing into conflict [16].

In Africa, security institutions which are established with the responsibility of managing conflicts are too weak and not governed by the norms and principles of democracy [20]. Despite the fact that some modifications have been taken by the leaders of African states, they solely serve the elite and the regimes than that of the society in general (Ibid). Hence, the AU cognizant of the limitations of security institutions had adopted its own policy framework on SSR in 2008. It was adopted with the intent of managing the overriding security problems and lack of African ownership of the current SSR among member states [2].

The SSR in Ethiopia was introduced in 2002 by the Justice System Reform Program Office under the authority of Ministry of Capacity Building and latter named as the Comprehensive Justice Sector Reform Program (JSRP) in the year 2005 [26]. The ultimate goal of the JSRP was to create an environment whereby the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens are protected via maintaining the rule of law and good governance. It was adopted under the auspices of donor countries like UK and Norwegian government [30]. However, the SSR program is solely driven by the government without the participation of the public and with little room for democracy and predominantly focused on the military forces [29].

In order to have a successful economic, political and social development, there should be a secured environment in which the safety, stability and integrity of a given society are achieved [22]. To do so, the SSR is an indispensable aspect of all forms of development at the national or local levels. According to [21], SSR is an essential element of any development and it must come even before economic development. If the personal and state security is achieved, the need for economic security will come next (Ibid). Therefore, the existence of SSR in a normative and pragmatic manner is pertinent not only to ensure security and justice but also to have an all rounded development.

The SSR or the JSRP in Ethiopia was launched for the sake of reforming security institutions in a way that they would provide efficient and effective services in accordance with the law; enhance public participation in crime prevention; to make Police Force accountable and transparent; and to create a professional security apparatus via establishing police colleges at federal and regional levels [26]. However, scholars suggested that the reform program is plagued with high politicization and excessive intervention of the higher executive officials [18]. As such, it poses a question over the practical implementation of SSR in Ethiopia.

Pertaining to the studies little has been done on SSR in Ethiopia in general and in Amhara Regional State police force in particular. Even the existing studies are limited to assess the current implementation, limitations and challenges of SSR in Police Force particularly in their service delivery in Amhara Region. Therefore, the fact that little empirical research had been conducted in the area makes the topic pertinent and timely. Hence, such gaps inspired the researcher to conduct further investigation and to fill the existing knowledge gap. The general objective of this study is to assess the current implementations, limitations and challenges of security sector reform in Ethiopia with a particular reference to Amhara National Regional State Police Force. Besides, this study is expected to answer the following research questions.

- How SSR is being implemented in the ANRS Police Commission?
- What are the challenges facing the implementation of SSR in Amhara Regional Police?
- What are the measures taken by the police and other governmental institutions to deal with these problems and improve service delivery?

2. DEFINITION OF TERMS AND CONCEPTS

The concept of security is included here because it is the major subject of my study, that is, security sector reform. Security as a concept is defined by different scholars differently. For example, [8] defined security as attaining one's freedom from threat that may endanger the life of individuals and the society at large. Security means a condition whereby individuals or the society as a whole are freed from threats such as from physical violence which hinders them doing whatever they like. However, the holistic definition of security is given by the Development Assistance Committee (DAC) Guideline reference document. Accordingly, security is:

“.....all-encompassing condition in which people and communities live in freedom, peace and safety, participate fully in the governance of their countries, enjoy the protection of fundamental rights, have access to resources and the basic necessities of life, and inhabit an environment which is not detrimental to their health and wellbeing. [11, p.20]

The traditional notion of security emphasized on the military strength of state and its protection from external aggression. But, this approach could not address the security threats of individuals and the community since the end of cold war had brought a new phase of conflict in the world particularly in developing nations. Since then, a new paradigm of security has been developed which moves away from state-centric conceptions of security to people-centric conceptions, thereby much attention are given for the security of the individuals, their protection from multitude threats and empowerment in general [32]. Hence, the concept of human security comes to exist which would be discussed below.

The shift of paradigm in the field of security led to the integration of the concept of human security. According to [31], the need for having a new paradigm of security is “in response to the complexity and the interrelatedness of both old and new security threats – from chronic and persistent poverty to ethnic violence, human trafficking, climate change, health pandemics, international terrorism, and sudden economic and financial downturns”(p.7). Therefore, human security is defined as protecting the essential values and rights of human kind in a way that they can achieve their freedom and fulfill their need.

Security sector is an institution established for the provision, management and supervision of security for people and the state [1]. It refers to those institutions of the society that are entrusted with the power to ensure the security of their lives and property in a certain geographical boundary [2]. The security sector institution encompasses the military, paramilitary, police, border guards, intelligence services, government bodies that monitor these organizations mentioned here and institutions that are charged with upholding the rule of law, including the judiciary and the penal system [11].

Security Sector Reform, in other words, is termed as security sector governance, security sector transformation, security sector development, security sector review as well as security and justice reform [2]. It is the process through which those security sector actors mentioned above adapt to

the political and organizational demands of transformation via adhering to the democratic norms and principles of good governance such as transparency, accountability, the rule of law, and adequate oversight of security systems in general [14]. Besides, it focuses on addressing the failure of states pertinent security institutions due to inefficiency, lack of professionalism, inadequate oversight mechanisms, corrupt practices and human rights violations (Ibid). But, to address its objective the reform, among other things, needs to shift from the traditional way of thinking of security to the modern one; modify the existing constitutional and institutional arrangement; establish strong and democratic civilian control of the security institutions; redefining the tasks and responsibilities of these institutions; and lastly there should be high forms of security integration and cooperation across the state [17].

However, the mere existence of SSR does not guarantee the overall security, wellbeing and development of citizens and state. Hence, [29] argued that to have a successful security sector reform, there must be democratic institutions in line with the realization of a democratic politics by the government, civil servants and security actors itself. Therefore, the existence of a genuine and democratic institution and the full fledged realization of democratic norms and principles are indispensable aspects for effective SSR. But, where there is deficient, mismanaged and unprofessional security institutions in a country, the government cannot afford and guarantee the security of its citizens and led them to ensure their security by other means. Hence, it will create a vacuum of security between the government and citizens and finally it begets the loss of state legitimacy [11]. Moreover, there are also others who contend that the successfulness or failures of SSR depends on leadership. According to Mr. Waldemar Vrey who speaks on the AU SSR forum stated that “the absence of strong leadership, or leadership that lacks credibility, is a major factor for the failure of SSR”. It implies that the commitment and dedication of leaders who are in power play paramount importance for the overall implementation of the principles of security sector reform. Generally, to have a sustainable security sector reform in a given country, there should be democratic institutions as well as vigilant and well-managed security personnel and officials.

3. THE CHALLENGES OF SECURITY SECTOR REFORM IN AFRICA

At the early inception of SSR in Africa, most of the States in the continent have understood that SSR would be pertinent for early recovery from protracted conflicts, sustaining their economic development and the whole peace building effort at the regional and international level [31]. However, the security sector reform was prone to divergent challenges that hampered not to meet its ultimate objective. According to [24], the challenges of SSR in developing countries, inter alia, encompass:

The Absence of a democratic culture and fragile institutions of democracy, weak governance (lacking authority, power, capacity and resources); internal security threats (insurgency, militia forces, a culture of warlords and gangs, violent crime); lack of staff (weak or no civilian departments); lack of Knowledge (the operational dimensions of civil-military relations); lack of functional skills (planning, budgeting, or financial control); Lack of advanced skills (threat analysis, formulation of policy, doctrine and legislation); lack of resource (communications, salaries, computers). [24, p.71]

For him the challenges for SSR in Africa emanate from African governments. In most cases, governments in Africa are not predictable due to the fact that the security policy is centralized

and captured by some group of political elites. Hence, leaders must be democratic enough and design policies which would benefit all.

But [19] argued that, the core problem of SSR in Africa stems mainly from its adoption by external forces which are characterized as piecemeal, narrow and short term in its strategic objective. Hence, for them the underlying problem of Africa's SSR is not only internally built, but it is due to the insertion of the program by foreigners without assimilating to the social and political context of African society. Therefore, SSR needs to be planted and implemented in line with the context of the society having broader and pragmatic objectives.

[20] On the other hand, pointed out the obstacles of reforming the security sector in Africa. Accordingly, the challenges of SSR in Africa is complex and attributed in the institutional nature of the security sector itself and it needs the rearrangement of such fragile institutions in such a way that there would be strong oversight of civilian and the community in general. To do so, it needs the commitment and dedication of leaders to implement the policies and strategies of SSR. Likewise, DAC in its guideline has also identified the constraints of SSR in Africa and it encompasses; lack of local ownership, lack of adequate funds, fragmented in implementation, lack of political will, weak government leadership and inter-agency collaboration, lack of transparency and participation, lack of policy and strategic frameworks [11]. Lack of local ownership, among other things, is a serious hindering factor for most Africa states. If the process of SSR is not shaped and run by local actors, it would be less likely to implement and achieve the intended outcome [29]. According to the United Nations Institute for Training and Research module guide locally owned SSR refers to "respect for local values and customs; flexibility and readiness to compromise; promotion of participatory approaches; people-centered (as opposed to elite-focused) SSR programs; civic empowerment/capacity building; donors take domestic actors seriously [33, p.11]. We can say that the SSR efforts made to reform the security sector or other development efforts are mostly driven by foreigners than local experts. So, if the African SSR needs to be successful, it should be driven and exercised by the local actors and stakeholders.

Hence, it is at this juncture that in most cases the African security institutions in general and the military and police in particular have shown unremitting deficiency in protecting the security and rights of its people. In this regard, [7] delineated that the security forces in Africa are the mirror of their colonial security institutions and solely served the security and wellbeing of their political elites than the society at large. Others also added that, many of the security problems in Africa stem from the security forces than from the people [25]. This implies that security forces in most cases in Africa are the sources of conflict because they are not executing their mandates as envisaged in the law. Therefore, the security forces in general and police and the military in particular should stand for the protection of the security and rights of the society in line with the prescribed laws.

4. MODERN POLICE IN ETHIOPIA

As historical evidences show, the emergence of modern police system in Ethiopia was started during the period of Menelik II in 1917, and named as *Arada Zebegna* [4]. But, the most holistic picture of modern police system was started by Emperor Haile Selassie I (1930-1974). During this period, the numbers of police officials have been increased in order to widen their scope and reach in every corner of the country [3]. Hence, for the sake of institutionalizing the police force in 1942, a distinct national police institution was established having its own power and function. The Ethiopian Police Proclamation No. 6/42 stipulated that "The force shall be employed for the

prevention of crime, the maintenance of peace and good order, apprehension of offenders, the safety of persons and property and the control of traffic". This proclamation had served as a baseline for the establishment of today's police structure and its guiding principles in general. However, the police department could not protect the rights and freedoms of citizens rather it served the regime and other nobilities in prolonging their power onto the downfall of Emperor Haile Selassie's regime (Haile Selassie, 1973) as cited in [34].

After the downfall of Emperor Haile Selassie's regime, the Dergue government came into power and the structure and composition of police was also changed. The Dergue regime was characterized by the facts that it transferred numbers of qualified police force to the national army and neutralized the police via delegating its power to different organizations (Markos, 2000, p.2) as cited in [3]. Like that of its predecessors, police force during the Dergue government had served the regime rather than citizens and led to the gross violations of rights and freedoms of citizens. Generally speaking, the development of police in the two consecutive regimes was characterized by the adoption of centralized police system and lack of clear objective and served the regime than that of the society in general.

Following the demise of the Dergue regime, the Ethiopian Federal Democratic Republic government came into power. Hence, the structure of police was reorganized under the policy of decentralization [34]. So, based on the decentralization policy today, the Ethiopian police forces are organized at federal and regional levels. According to the FDRE constitution Art 52(2) & (9), in addition to the federal police the nine regional states and two city administrative shall have their own police force which can be administered under their jurisdiction. The federal police force is accountable to the Ministry of Federal Affairs and the regional police force on the other hand is accountable to the Regional Security and Administrative Affairs Office [5].

The Amhara National Regional State which is one of the nine regional states in Ethiopia, established its police force under the power delegated by the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia constitution mentioned above. As a result, the police structure in the region is decentralized up to local administrative bodies (*kebeles*) and they provide services to the community vis-à-vis militias (*local security guards*).

4.1 WHY SSR IN ETHIOPIA?

The need and initiatives for adopting SSR across countries is different given the existing political, social and economic conditions. In most cases SSR is more likely needed for states which emerge from long and protracted conflict and instability [33]. It is intended to strengthen the overall peace building efforts which would be made to bring lasting peace and sustainable development by preventing the recurrence of conflict and protecting rights of citizens. Therefore, the need for adopting SSR is mainly with the objective of transforming the roles, responsibilities and actions of security institutions so that they will be managed and operated based on democratic norms and principles of good governance and contribute for the overall development endeavor of a state.

Coming to Ethiopia, the need to launch the SSR or locally known to be the JSRP is for different reasons. While the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia government came into power since 1991, it has tried to transform its institution in a way that they can contribute for sustainable development and ride out of poverty. Hence, the then Ministry of Civil Service (today's Public Service and Human Resource Development) has launched the 14 national capacity building programs. Of these programs, the justice sector reform program is one given due emphasis at the time [27]. Yet, in spite of the efforts made by the government to reform institutions at the time

such as the justice system, different problems have been manifested. Therefore, the need to launch the JSRP in Ethiopia was to avert these problems and facilitate the court system, improve law making procedures, strengthen the capacity of law enforcement bodies (prosecutors, police and prisons), enhance the capacity of the Ministry of Justice and law schools as well as legal training and research centers, and to improve the information communication technology management and skill of various justice institutions [9].

As a result, the Justice System Reform Program in Ethiopia was launched in 2002 under the authority of Ministry of Capacity Building (today's Public Service and Human Resource Development) as a means to take remedies on the weaknesses of the justice system and to assess the performance of institutions like the court, prosecutor and police, and finally suggest some possible reforms [26]. It has five major components and it includes: i) Law making and revision; ii) the judiciary; iii) the law enforcement bodies particularly the police, public prosecutor, prisons; iv) legal education, training and legal research; v) access to justice like legal information, the bar, legal aid and alternative dispute resolution [15]. Therefore, the police reform program is an integral part of the wider Justice System Reform Program launched at the national level.

In order to achieve the objective of SSR particularly in police force, different measures have been undertaken by the government of Ethiopia. For example, to ensure the transparency, accountability, effectiveness and efficiency and public participation, short and long term training have been given; community policing are being implemented; modern information systems like forensic laboratory also incorporated which would facilitate the service delivery of security institutions [27]. Besides these, different programs such as BPR/Business Process Re-engineering, BSC/Balanced Score Card, citizens' charter and system of handling complaints have been incorporated to strengthen the service delivery and effectiveness of security and justice institutions [12]. BPR refers to changing the overall structure and process of a certain organization to bring radical improvement. BSC is strategic plan used to be implemented through measuring the performance of workers in a government institution [27]. Indeed, the inaugurations of such programs to some existent have changed the modes of operation and service delivery of justice and security institutions in general. In addition to the efforts made by the government, different donors such as World Bank, EU, USA, Canada, France, Netherland, Sweden, Norway and UK and provide support through their agencies [30].

However, in spite of the efforts made to improve the security institutions in general and police forces in particular, the reform remains to be below the expected outcome. There are different reasons why the reform program has taken a back seat in Ethiopia. The reform program among others is merely driven by the government without intensive public participation and with little room for democracy and good governance. Besides, as mentioned above the reform program has included many projects and these projects were supposed to be implemented within a short period of time. It also hampered the reform programs not to be implemented on the given time schedule.

According to the Ministry of Justice and Regional Justice Bureaus 2007-2010/11 report on justice sector stated that the justice system or the reform program could not adequately make law enforcement bodies to embrace the principles of transparency and accountability in practice with little room for the participation of different stakeholders. In addition, the Netherland based Center for International Legal Cooperation (CILC) asserted that the security institutions in general and the police, courts and prosecutors in particular lack accountability and could not adhere to the rule of law [26]. Therefore, we can say that the Ethiopian SSR in general and police reform in

particular is not in a position to make police force adhere to the fundamental objectives and principles of SSR envisaged by the country and other international institutions .

Generally speaking, the current condition under which the Ethiopian JSRP and the police reform activities operating across different security force remains to be lip-service than improving their service delivery in practice. The reform programs are not well articulated and designed in line with protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens and could not enable the police force to provide efficient and effective service via adhering to the principles of transparency and accountability. It also lacks clear objective that needs to be achieved in each police department. Consequently, the overall performance of the JSRP and police reform remains to be at stake and it shows that the reform could not improved the service delivery of different justice and security institutions like the police, courts, prosecutors and prisons. Therefore, the police reform programs are not designed in a manner that can improve the effectiveness and accountability of police force in general. Indeed some attempts which are made either by the government or donors countries are commendable. But, still much more efforts are needed from the government and other stakeholders to improve the current status of JSRP and police reform in Ethiopia.

4.2 THE CHALLENGES OF SSR AND POLICE REFORM IN ETHIOPIA

Even though the JSRP and police reform was established by setting fascinating objectives which are mentioned above, the program is overwhelmed with different constraints or challenges. According to the Comprehensive Justice System reform Program Base Line study report, the Ethiopian Justice System in general encountered the following challenges:

Firstly, it is neither accessible nor responsive to the needs of the poor. Secondly, serious steps to tackle corruption, abuse of power and political interference in the administration of justice have yet to be taken. Thirdly, inadequate funding of the justice institutions aggravates most deficiencies of the administration of justice. The perception of the independence of the Judiciary is very low. The system of justice in Ethiopia is generally characterized by delays in the dispensation of justice, lack of institutional capacity in law enforcement, court and inefficient system of law enforcement and congestion and creates obstacles in the promotion and protection of human and democratic rights, inefficiencies in law enforcement as well as in the administration of justice. [26, p.14].

In the same fashion, [18] also revealed the Ethiopian JSRP and police reform in particular is attributed in high politicization and tightly controlled by the higher executive bodies of the ruling government which is geared to achieve political ends. Likewise, Elias argued that the reform program at its early phase was too ambitious followed by fragmentation of the reform process with inadequate grassroots empowerment and harmonization [15]. In this regard, the Organization for Economic cooperation and Development stated that while setting goals, it is advisable to be specific, realistic, achievable and pragmatic other than being over ambitious [11]. But, the Ethiopian JSRP was aimed at addressing the problems of all justice institutions within a short time interval. One of the basic pillars to have an effective SSR is the prevalence of strong oversight control by the parliament or civilian. However, lack of strong oversight control by the parliament of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia government is also one of the challenges that the Ethiopian JSRP faces today (ibid). And loosely oversight control of the security sector would exacerbate corrupt practices and injustices and which, in turn, led to violation of rights of citizens.

In addition, Ato Mandefro Belay who was the then head of Justice System Reform Program Office in the Ministry of Capacity Building stated that “One of the main challenges in the implementation of the Justice System Reform Program has been its complexity and the desire to undertake many reform projects in a short time” [quoted in 15]. Ironically, this guy also pointed out the other challenges of JSR and delineated that the reform program in its initial plan lacks to inculcate other important sectors of the Justice System like the role of civil associations in justice System and social courts/traditional courts (Ibid). Therefore, in order to compromise such paradox, there should be a mechanism whereby regular based assessment of the JSR and police reform programs be envisaged under the authority of the Ethiopian Federal Democratic Republic Ministry of Public Service and Human Resource Development which has the authority to do so.

5. METHODOLOGY

In this research, the researcher employed qualitative research approach. Qualitative research approach helps to examine the decision, attitude, and behavior of people or other phenomena in depth. To this end, this method enabled the researcher to study the behavior, experience, and performance of police force in their distinctive institution. Since the research problem by its nature needs an investigation of the experience and attitude of the research participants on the reform program, qualitative research method was the most appropriate one. As a result, the researcher used this approach to assess the current implementation, limitations and challenges of SSR in the Amhara National Regional Police Commission.

The researcher employed a case study research design. It is also important for studying a topic which is not given a due emphasis by any previous researchers. Since, the intent of the researcher is to investigate the current implementation, challenges and limitations of SSR in Amhara Regional Police institution and employing case study was the most appropriate design. In order to select participants, the researcher employed Non-probability Sampling techniques. Hence, the data were collected from the Amhara Regional Police Commissioners, the Commission’s Unit leaders, Police Officers, Special Forces and from the ANRS Administrative and Security Affairs Bureau Officers. Besides these, one of the Kefile Ketema’s located in Bahir Dar City Shimbit Kifle ketema Police Station was selected purposefully. It was selected because of the fact that this K/Ketema has a profound interaction with the ANRS Police Commission. Accordingly, officers who are working in the police station were interviewed.

The researcher has interviewed participants until he get new ideas/ the views of participants are repeated on the same interview questions. Accordingly, the researcher used a total of 28 participants, of which five of them were key informant, ten semi-structured interviewees and thirteen FGD discussants. And they provided their response based on the interview questions provided by the researcher.

In order to get the appropriate data different techniques, both primary and secondary source have been used. Primary sources of data are collected through Semi-structured interview, Key informant interview and Focus Group Discussion. Whereas, secondary sources of data were collected through document review. Hence, the following documents such as; journals, books, reports (at international, national and regional levels), thesis/dissertations were consulted. But in order to get relevant and empirical data, the researcher has relied more importantly on primary sources of data. The collected data was analyzed through thematic analysis technique. It is essential to associate an analysis of the frequency of a theme with one of the whole content and

give opportunity to understand any issue in a wider spectrum [23] Therefore, the data collected via interview, key informant and focus group discussion were analyzed thematically.

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

6.1 THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SSR

According to the participants SSR/JSRP practiced in their institution through different reform tools like BPR and BSC. The ANRS Justice System Reform Plan since 2011-2015 affirmed that the justice system reform program encompasses the judiciary and law enforcement bodies. It is aimed to speed up democracy and good governance, ensure rule of law and respect for the rights and freedoms of citizen. Accordingly, the JSRP includes three subprograms, i.e. justice sector reform sub-program; law enforcement bodies (Police, prosecutor and prisons) reform sub-program; legal education, training and research reform sub-program. Each sub-program has specific projects to be accomplished within each institution. For example, the law enforcement body reform sub-program has 31 projects and one of these projects is police force capacity building project (the ANRS justice Bureau GTP I JSRP Plan document, 2011).

Therefore, the study concluded that the reform program in the ANRS is practiced through different sub-projects and programs. But in the case of ANRS Police Commission, it is practiced in the form of the so-called civil service reform tools (BPR, BSC and 1 to 5 arrangements) and through the establishment of community policing program. Besides, it is also tightly controlled by one of the regional executive body (the ANRS Administrative and Security Affairs Bureau).

6.2 CHALLENGES OF POLICE REFORM PROGRAM IN ANRS POLICE COMMISSION

Challenges are those hindering factor that contributes for the low performance and inadequate implementation of SSR. Hence, there are different challenges that hampered the police reform programs not to be implemented genuinely in the ANRS Police force and it includes;

Political Interference: undesirable interference of government officials is the major hindering factor that affects the reform programs in the study area. Most of the interviewees indicated that the Police institution should be non-partisan/run its activities independently and serve the people equally. However, the structural arrangement of the Police Commission is accountable to the ANRS Administrative and Security Affairs Bureau and everything should pass through this institution. Therefore, from the outset the Commission is not strictly separated and functioned independently provided that it is under the control of the ANRS Administrative and Security Affairs Bureau. Therefore, the study concluded that lack of strict separation from other government institutions and the tightly control and interference of officials from such institutions has affected the overall reform activities of the police force in the ANRS Police Commission.

Lack of Competent Leadership: The other challenge that hinders the reform programs not to meet its objective is lack of competent and effective leader. Those leaders assigned in different positions of the ANRS Police Commission are not based on their merit rather they are appointed based on their affiliation/dedication to the ruling party/government. This, in turn, led to the backlash performance of the institution in general and the police force in particular. So it is plausible to say that lack of quality leadership in security institutions has an impact on the overall implementation of SSR and the service delivery of police force.

Inadequate Resources: it includes insufficient number of both human and material resources in the institution. The reforms program in the ANRS Police Commission had no sufficient human and material resources. The police commission is understaffed. Even the existing personnel are not well trained and lack skill to use different technologies. Besides, the material resources are also inadequate which affects the reform program. For example, those technologies and materials such as; C.C.TV Camera (Close Circuit TV Camera), modern guns (Shotgun, Handgun etc), Masks, Vehicles and Motorcycles and biochemical laboratory which are used for forensic investigation are not fulfilled.

Lack of Continuous Capacity Building: There is also lack of continuous and consistent capacity building. One of the reform tools used to enhance the capacity of police officers is through providing short or long term trainings on different issues such as on protecting the rights of citizens; proper handling mechanisms of citizens who are suspects in custody; utilization of modern technologies; the code of conduct and mechanisms of accountability and others. The Amhara National Regional State Zikre Hig under part two article 3 (a, b and c) stated that police forces shall take basic police training related to their professional and service competency (the ANRS Zikre Hig February 25th, 2004). However, in spite of some efforts made to provide trainings, much has not yet done. In other words, it is not given due emphasis by the government and other stakeholders.

Lack of Adequate Budget and other Incentives: There is also lack of adequate budget that hindered the reform program in the ANRS Police Commission. The problem stems from the federal level and goes down to the regional level. And failure to allocate budget for police institutions directly affects the overall human development activities. This is so because where there is no budget, academic institutions which are primarily aimed to improve human development in different police institutions could not be expanded and strengthened. It hinders police force not to discharge their duties effectively and efficiently. Moreover, the salary and other incentives paid for the Police Force is low as compared with other civil servants. They task of Police is 24 hours, but the salary and other payments are disproportional.

Generally, among the challenges of the reform program in the ANRS Police Commission mentioned above, political interference, lack of adequate human and material resources and competent leadership are the most serious problems

6.3 MEASURES TAKEN TO ADDRESS CHALLENGES

In order to improve the reform program and service delivery of police, different measures have been undertaken so far by the ANRS Police Commission and stakeholders. For example, to address lack of adequate budget they mobilize the people to contribute something for the police force through collecting different material particularly from hotels and resort owners. They sell the collected materials via bid and generate funds. Besides, in order to have consistent capacity building in the ANRS police force, the Commission has started to create link with some NGOs which are found in Bahir Dar city like Finote Hiwot and World vision. Despite the fact that such attempts are there in the ANRS Police Commission, measures are not consistent and up to the standard. They are rather fragmented and situational in nature. Therefore, it is concluded that in most cases the measures taken by the ANRS Police Commission to improve the police reform program and their service delivery are limited to the staffs of the Commission. In the sense, measures are not adequately addressed to the members of police officers working in different stations of Bahir Dar City.

The roles of Stakeholders in the ANRS Police Commission are also limited. The first stakeholders are those bodies which have a direct involvement such as; the ANRS Administrative and Security Affairs Bureau, civil service Bureau, Red Cross, Prison Commission, Office of Militia and Justice Bureau. On the other hand, the second stakeholders are institutions which have no direct involvement in the Commission and it includes; the society, Universities, women and child Bureau, media, NGOs (World Vision, Finote Hiwot and others). Hence, the first stakeholders are those governmental institutions that have an obligation to provide support for Police Commission and police force at large. The contributions of such institutions are not sufficient enough. For example, the ANRS Administrative and Security Affairs Bureau is one of the stakeholders of the ANRS Police Commission. But, it's role is not that much adequate and significant enough.

As the finding of [12] rightly mentioned, the role and engagement of civil societies in SSR programs in Ethiopia is very limited because of different reasons. As such, the effectiveness of SSR remains to be at stake given that the engagements of civil societies are insufficient. Therefore, the role of stakeholders to improve the reform program and service delivery of police is not well planned and adequate enough, with the exception of some movements.

7. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

The study was intended to assess the current implementations, limitations and challenges of Security Sector Reform in Ethiopia with a particular reference to the Amhara National Regional State Police Commission. The study set out major objectives and to meet these objectives, research questions were prepared. Accordingly, the first finding of the study shows that SSR is practiced in the Amhara National Regional State Police Commission. It is practiced in the form of BPR, BSC, and 1: 5 arrangements and through community policing. But it is not exclusively compiled and documented as it there in other security institutions in Ethiopia.

The study also concluded that the police reform programs in the ANRS Police Commission are not effective enough to improve the service delivery of police force in particular and the whole structural organization of the Commission in general. Even some reform programs are missing its objectives and serve as a political instrument for the government at large. This study has identified the major challenges of the police reform in the ANRS Police Commission. These include; political interference, lack of competent leadership, inadequate resources, lack of continuous capacity building, lack of access for education, lack of adequate budget and incentives. Hence, the study concluded that political interference, lack of human and material resources and competent leadership are the most serious challenges that affected the reform programs in the ANRS Police Commission.

Based on the findings of the study, the measures taken by the ANRS Police Commission and other stakeholders to improve the reform programs are inadequate. So while measures are taken it should be inclusive and consistent. The role of civil societies including different NGOs working on security and justice sector in the ANRS Police Commission is very limited. This is so, because of the fact that the 2009 Charities and Societies Proclamation adopted by the parliament of our country (Ethiopia) restricted the contribution of different non-governmental institutions.

Lastly, the study concluded that in order to improve the effectiveness of the police reform program and service delivery of police force in the ANRS Police Commission the most serious challenges that are mentioned above should be solved as soon as possible. In addition, Stakeholders like NGOs should have the room to fully participate in the reform activities of the

Commission. If so, the service delivery of police force will be improved and this, in turn, leads to protection of the rights of citizens and ensure good governance and democracy at large.

REFERENCE

- [1] Abegunde, O. (2013). Need for security sector reform: Nigerian perspective. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(9), 228-229.
- [2] African Union Commission. (2008). AU Policy framework on Security Sector Reform. Retrieved from [https:// www.peaceau.org/.../au-policy-framework-on-security-sector-reform-a](https://www.peaceau.org/.../au-policy-framework-on-security-sector-reform-a)
- [3] Alemayehu, S. (2010). Evaluating the application of human rights principles in crime Investigation in Ethiopia (a case study of the Addis Ababa city police) (Master's thesis, University of South Africa).
- [4] Andargachew, T. (2004). *The Crime Problem and Its Correction*, 2, Addis Ababa University press, Addis Ababa.
- [5] Baker, B. (2013). Hybridity in Policing: the Case of Ethiopia. *The Journal of Legal Pluralism and Unofficial Law*, 45(3), 296-313.
- [6] Ball, N. (1998). *Spreading Good Practices in Security Sector Reform: Policy Options for the British Government*. London: Safer world.
- [7] Bendix, D. and Stanley, R. (2008). Security Sector Reform in Africa: The Promise and the Practice of a New Donor Approach: Occasional Paper Series. African Centre for the Constructive Resolution of Disputes, 3(2), 9-11.
- [8] Buzan, B. (1991). Security according to Buzan: a comprehensive security analysis. *Security discussion papers series*, (1),5.
- [9] Crisis Management Initiative. (2008). Governance Out of a Box: ICT4State-Building-African Experiences and Opportunities Retrieved from <https://www.reliefweb.int/.../governance-out-box-ict4state-building-african-experie...>
- [10] Critchely, B. (1967). *A History of Police in England and Wales*. London: Constable and Company.
- [11] DAC Guideline and Reference Series. (2005). Security system reform and governance. Retrieved from <https://www.oecd.org/dac/governance-peace/.../docs/31785288.pdf>
- [12] Demelash K, (2011, April 23). The Ethiopian Justice System, Current Reform Efforts, Assessment and Recommendations (Blog post).
- [13] Edmunds, T. (2002). Security Sector Reform: Concepts and Implementation. Retrieved from https://www.dcaf.ch/content/download/36494/528205/file/01_Edmunds.pdf
- [14] Ejdus, F.(2009). Concept of security sector reform. Security challenges. Retrieved from [https://www.bezbednost.org/.../Filip-Ejdus.../location_in_text\[D\]=1](https://www.bezbednost.org/.../Filip-Ejdus.../location_in_text[D]=1)
- [15] Elias, N. (2015). Legal Sector Reform Pursuits in Ethiopia: Gaps in Grassroots Empowerment. *Mizan Law Review*, 9(3), 259-262.doi: 10.4314/mlr.v9i2.2
- [16] Hänggi, H. and Scherrer, V. (Eds.). (2007). *Recent Experience of UN Integrated Missions in Security Sector Reform*. Geneva.
- [17] Hedzic, M. (2004). The Concept of Security Sector. In Fluri, P. and Hedzic, M. (Eds). *Source book on Security Sector Reform: Collection of Papers* (pp.11-43). Belgrade: Geneva Centre for the Democratic Control of Armed Forces Centre for Civil-Military Relations.
- [18] Henoke, G. (2014, November 13-14). Justice sector reform, judicial independence and a diminished judicial power in Ethiopia: lesson from South Africa. Paper presented in the on the twenty years of South Africa constitutionalism workshop.

- [19] Hutchful, E. and Fayami, J.K, (2005). Security System Reform in Africa. DAC guidelines and reference series.
- [20] Joseph, L. (2003). Security sector reform in Africa: Relevance to peace building.
- [21] Le Grys, B. (2010). British Military Involvement in Sierra Leone, 2001-2006, In P. Jackson & P. Albrecht (Eds.), Security sector reform in Sierra Leone 1997-2007: Views from the front line (pp39-57).
- [22] Marenin, O. (2013). Policing reform and economic development in African States: understanding the link: empowering change. The wider working paper. Helsinki, Finland
- [23] Marks, D. and Yardley, L. (2004). Research methods for clinical and health psychology. SAGE
- [24] Medhane, T. (2007). Overcoming Challenges to Security Sector Reform in the Horn of Africa. In Roux L.and Yemane K. (Eds.), Challenges to Security Sector Reform in Horn of Africa (pp.70-75).
- [25] Mehler, A. (2009). The Production of Insecurity by African Security Forces: Insights from Liberia and the Central Africa Republic. GIGA Working Paper. Hamburg, Germany.
- [26] Ministry of Capacity Building, Justice System Reform Program Office. (2005). Comprehensive Justice System Reform Program: Baseline Study Report. Addis Ababa: Ethiopia.
- [27] Ministry of Civil Service. (2013). The Civil Service Reform Program in Ethiopia. Addis Ababa.
- [28] Mishler, W. and Rose, R. (1998). Trust in Untrustworthy Institutions: Culture and Institutional Performance in Post-communist Societies. Glasgow: Centre for the Study of Public Policy.
- [29] Nathan, L., Arévalo, B.D., Mulugeta G.B., Conteh, K., Ebo, A., & Sky, E. (2007). Local ownership of security sector reform: A guide for donors. The UK Government's Global Conflict Prevention Pool
- [30] Skaar, E., Samset, I., and Gloppen, S., (2004). Aid to judicial reform: Norwegian and international experience.
- [31] UN Commission for Human Security. (2003). Human security now. Protecting and empowering the people. Retrieved from <https://reliefweb.int/report/.../human-security-now-protecting-and-empowering...>
- [32] United Nation Security Sector Reform Unit. (2011). The United Nations SSR Perspective. Retrieved from <http://www.un.org/en/events/peacekeepersday/pdf/securityreform.pdf>
- [33] United Nations Institute for Training and Research. (2014). Introduction to Security Sector Reform. Foundation Course. Retrieved from <https://www.unitar.org/.../introduction-security-sector-reform-tp2014>
- [34] Yeshiwas Degu. (2014). Community Policing or Policing the Community: The Emerging Police Practice in Ethiopia. International Journal of Science and Research, 3(9), 1948-195

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